

Uterine Perforation by LNG- Intrauterine Device: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

The intrauterine device LNG-IUD is the most popular method of reversible contraception in women of reproductive age nowadays, and its use is being reported by nearly 160 million women. It is considered safe and effective, but intrauterine devices are associated with rare complications such as uterine perforation. We report a case of uterine perforation by LNG-IUD, and to create awareness of the diagnosis and the laparoscopic management of these rare cases.

INTRODUCTION

Uterine perforation is an uncommon yet well-known complication of copper intrauterine devices and the levonorgestrel intrauterine system (IUS). While initial extrauterine placement at the time of insertion is felt to be the cause of perforation in most cases, some hypothesize that delayed transmural migration and subsequent perforation can occur with slightly malposition or even properly placed devices. The safety and effectiveness of modern intrauterine devices have been improved, and they are considered nowadays a low-risk method of birth control. However, some rare complications such as uterine perforation may have dangerous consequences. Physician awareness is crucial in how to diagnose and manage a patient with such a complication.

CASE REPORT

A 25-year-old woman presented to ED from sexual health clinic after insertion of LNG - IUD as she had severe vasovagal attack after LNG - IUD insertion at sexual health clinic. She was complaining of severe suprapubic and epigastric pain just after insertion of LNG - IUD. Her vital showed tachycardia and low blood pressure. On clinical examination she looked pale. On abdominal examination there was mild tenderness in suprapubic and epigastric area. LNG-IUD threads were not visible during the speculum examination, a Transvaginal ultrasound was requested that revealed an anteverted normal sized uterus with an endometrial thickness of 4 mm and an empty uterine cavity. An abdominopelvic anteroposterior and sagittal X-ray was requested that revealed a satisfactory bowel gas pattern, and the above IUD was showed to be in the central pelvis in the proximity of the uterus. She was booked for Hysteroscopy + Diagnostic Laparoscopy + Removal of Mirena Coil + Pelvic washout. Full blood count and routine bloods were requested at laparoscopy, the uterus was found to be normal size anteverted uterus with small area of perforation noted, not bleeding and measuring less than 0.5cm, arising

near R ostium, tube intact. Normal upper abdominal organs. - Site of perforation from R ostium with no surrounding structures involved. The LNG -IUD was found in Pouch of Douglas, -- Clear pelvic fluid, no bloody or bowel contents, not attached to any other structures. Mirena threads grasped and easily removed through LIF 10mm port. Copious washout, area of perforation dries with no active bleeding. The device was inspected to verify its integrity The hysteroscopic inspection of the uterine cavity revealed no portion of the coil embedded in the uterine wall. The patient was discharged home the following day. And her recovery was unremarkable.

DISCUSSION

Over the years, perforation of the uterus by IUD has become a rare phenomenon with a reported overall incidence of 1.1-1.4 in 1,000 insertions. Uterine perforation may occur at the time of primary insertion or later on caused by gradual damage to the uterine wall. Over the years, perforation of the uterus by IUD has become a rare phenomenon with a reported overall incidence of 1.1-1.4 in 1,000 insertions. Uterine perforation may occur at the time of primary insertion or later on caused by gradual damage to the uterine wall with the most common symptoms being abdominal pain and the absence of IUD threads or an unexpected pregnancy. However, in cases of uterine perforation, copper IUD causes more adhesions than LNG-IUD, a phenomenon likely due to the toxic effects of copper ions and the ability of copper IUD to cause local inflammation. Therefore, the surgical removal of an abdominal copper coil is likely to be more challenging than in the case of an LNG-IUD. Operative laparoscopy, as performed in this case, is the preferred method for removing a perforated IUD, and its safety has been advocated widely.

CONCLUSION

Although LNG-IUDs are considered safe, there is a small chance of uterine perforation in about 0.9-1 in 1,000 insertions when performed mainly by general practitioners. It is important to know that more than 90% of perforations are not diagnosed at the time of insertion and more than 50% of perforations are detected more than a year after the insertion. Given a positive correlation between the time of insertion and with the possibility of severe damage to intra-abdominal organs, physician awareness is crucial to make an early diagnosis, especially if there is a lack of visualization of the IUD threads, that should prompt the physician to request further investigations such as a vaginal ultrasound and on the suspicion of uterine perforation, laparoscopy should be strongly considered.

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